

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
School of Engineering

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

TIDAL TURBINE BLADE COMPOSITES USING BASALT FIBRE REINFORCED POWDER EPOXY

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I. Tidal energy market

- Tidal market projections worldwide: 23%CAGR/annum¹.
- Small and emerging market (significantly smaller than wind energy^{2,3}). Advantage is predictability.
- Water density 800 times higher than air: high quality fibres composites required.
- Tidal blades smaller than wind (8- 12m length).
- Scotland important contributor within tidal sector: Alstom, Atlantis Resources, Orbital Marine Power, all based in the Pentland Firth, Scotland.
- Very good energy production figures reported.
- Edinburgh University: first dedicated tidal blade testing facility⁴ (EPSRC): **FASTBLADE**.

Alstom TGO 1MW capacity

Atlantis 1.5 MW capacity

Orbital Marine Power
2MW capacity

FASTBLADE facility

¹ <https://www.marketwatch.com/press-release/wave-and-tidal-energy-market-growth-industry-trends-report-2022-2018-05-21>

² <https://marineenergy.biz/2018/03/12/global-installed-ocean-energy-power-doubles-in-2017/>

³ <https://wwwindea.org/blog/2018/02/12/2017-statistics/>

⁴ <https://www.fastblade.eng.ed.ac.uk/>

I. MARINCOMP & POWDERBLADE

- EU FP7 Marie Curie Project led by the University of Edinburgh & UCC (2014-2018). Other partners include Toray Carbon Fibres, Suzlon, Ulster University and Orbital Marine Energy.
- Development of novel carbon-fibre reinforced powder-epoxy composite materials tailored for long-term durability in the marine environment.

- EU Horizon 2020 involving the University of Edinburgh, ÉireComposites, Suzlon and WestBIC (2017-2019).
- Research of novel manufacturing routes for large wind turbine blade processing using powder epoxy based hybrid carbon/glass composites.

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I. Objectives

- Demonstrate the superior manufacturing abilities of the towpregging tapeline.
- Investigate and characterise the mechanical properties of epoxy powder based BFRP.
- Optimisation of epoxy powder based composites.
- Compare the mechanical properties of towpreg based BFRP using basalt fibres from 2 different providers.
- Upscale manufacturing for out-of-autoclave industrial purposes.
- Tidal turbine blade market : investigate the influence of water immersion¹ on BFRP mechanical properties.

¹P. Alam, C. Robert, C.M. Ó Brádaigh, Tidal turbine blade composites - a review on the effects of hygrothermal aging on the properties of CFRP, Composites Part B: Engineering, 149, 2018, 248-259.

II. Powder epoxy advantages

- **Principle: powder melts on fibres (towpreg) followed by curing of the epoxy (heat activation).**
- **Low minimal viscosity (low molecular weight) during melting phase: optimal wetting¹.**
- **Low curing exotherm (1/3rd of standard resin), reducing the risk of thermal runaway in composite thick sections¹.**
- **Good for very thick composite sections (large wind and tidal blades).**

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Parallel-plate Rheometry

¹C. Robert, D. Mamalis, P. Alam, A.D. Lafferty, C. Ó Cadhain, G. Breathnach, E.D. McCarthy, C.M. Ó Brádaigh, Powder Epoxy Based UD-CFRP Manufacturing Routes For Turbine Blade Application”, SAMPE 2018, Southampton, 2018

²James Maguire, Kapileswar Nayak, Conchur M Ó Brádaigh, Characterisation of epoxy powders for processing thick-section composite structures, Materials & Design 2018.

II. Industrial incentive

Powder epoxy with glass fibre

*13.0m wind turbine blades
manufactured by ÉireComposites*

*Patented electrically-heated
ceramic mould tooling*

- One piece moulding - no gluing of spars to skins
→ one shot cure, cost reduction.
- Low exotherm: reduces risks and allows quicker manufacturing, cost reduction.
- Powder and towpreg can be stored in a standard environment and ambient temperature for an extended amount of time.
- Need heated tooling¹ (c. 180°C) – electrically-heated.
- Quality control of fibre direction and wet-out can be carried out prior to final assembly.
- Easily upscale for out-of-autoclave industrial purposes?

II. Basalt fibres

- **Basalt fibres: naturally sourced (volcanic rock), different chemical composition → quality variation depending on the basalt deposit quality¹.**
- **Basalt fibres from two suppliers (MAFIC and BASALTEX) were selected.**
- **On paper, the properties of the fibres were identical: a strength of 3.0 GPa and a stiffness of 87.0 GPa^{2,3}.**

→ Compare the mechanical properties of unidirectional basalt fibre composites (UD-BFRP).

Basaltic rocks

Basalt fibres bobbins

¹V. Fiore, T. Scalici, G. Di Bella, A. Valenza, A review on basalt fibre and its composites, Composites Part B: Engineering, 74, 2015, 74-94.

²http://www.basaltex.com/files/cms1/basaltfibersbasicproperties_636669004437905000.pdf

³<http://www.matweb.com/search/datasheet.aspx?matguid=c651e59ea1e7429597911888a2fb2a5d&ckck=1>
© Basaltex (<http://www.basaltex.com/en/about-basalt.aspx>)

III. Overall process

6 stage process:

1. Bobbin tows and powder epoxy are placed in the towpregging tapeline
2. Basalt tape is produced (next slide for details).
3. Basalt towpreg cut into 30 cm length strips and weighted to achieve the right fibre volume fraction (50%).
4. Basalt strips are aligned in a custom made tensioning device.
5. The whole device is placed under vacuum and cured.
6. A powder epoxy, towpreg-based unidirectional BFRP plate is ready for use. Samples are extracted and tested.

Overview of process from basalt tows to plate manufacturing and testing

III. Towpregging tapeline

- 2 step process: towpreg manufacturing then composite processing.
- Manufacturing upscale in scope of Automated Tape Placement (ATP) processing.
- Quick, reliable, reproducible, better mechanical properties than vacuum assisted resin infusion.

Towpreg manufacturing unit: electrostatic powder deposition gun, fibre heating zone and tow winding

Towpregging tapeline in operation (with carbon fibre tow)

III. Fibre alignment & curing procedure

Fibre alignment

Layer by layer process

BFRP Plate after curing

- Lengthy process but good manufacturing control.
- Fibres kept under tension the whole process for superior mechanical properties.
- Composite via powder based epoxy initial proof of concept.
- Next step: Automated Fibre Placement processing.

IV. Static mechanical properties

- **Good mechanical properties compared to literature¹⁻⁴: fibres kept under tension throughout, superior fibre alignment.**
- **In tension 0°, Basaltex fibres displayed superior strength and stiffness compared to Mafic fibres.**
- **In tension 90°, higher stiffness was found for Basaltex, suggesting better interfacial properties as the epoxy powder was the same in both cases.**

¹P. Davies, W. Verboouwe, Evaluation of Basalt fibre Composites for Marine Applications, *Applied composite Materials*, **25**, 2, 2018, 299-308.

²W. Chen, H. Shen, M.L. Auad, C. Huang, S. Nutt, Basalt fiber-epoxy laminates with functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **40**, 2009, 1082-1089.

³A. Dorigato, A. Pegoretti, Fatigue resistance of basalt fibers-reinforced laminates, *Journal of Composite materials*, **46**, 15, 2011, 1773-1785.

⁴V. Lopresto, C. Leone, I. De Iorio, Mechanical characterization of basalt fibre reinforced plastic, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **42**, 2011, 717-723.

IV. Static mechanical properties

- 4 point flexure and compression testing also revealed superior properties for Basaltex fibres, confirming the results obtained in tension.
- Basalt fibres are naturally sourced and their chemical composition varies from one location to the other, which explains the mismatch between both BFRP mechanical properties.

IV. Water ageing

- Application for tidal turbine blades: influence of water ageing on UD-BFRP mechanical properties?
- Two sets of samples aged at 21°C and 55°C. The temperature had an influence on both the sorption speed and water saturation level.
- The samples were tested in tension 0° and compared to their dry counterparts: a 13% reduction in strength and 11% in stiffness per percent of water ingress was observed, which is much lower than literature results^{1,2}.

V. Conclusion

- **Towpregging CF tapeline is an alternative material to resin infusion of CF for large composite structures.**
- **Versatility and adaptability of the towpreg is an industrial advantage, reducing cost and allowing better processing abilities.**
- **Tapeline-based samples exhibited superior mechanical properties compared to literature, due to tensioning system and low viscosity of epoxy before gel.**
- **Two basalt fibres providers have been selected and their products tested.**
- **Better mechanical properties was found for Basaltex fibres based towpreg powder-epoxy UD-BFRP.**
- **The mismatch of mechanical properties obtained highlight the importance of the basaltic rock source.**

Questions?

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